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ARE ADVISORS THE PRIMARY PROVIDERS OF INNOVATION SUPPORT SERVICES IN FORESTRY AND AGRICULTURE? PRELIMINARY FINDINGS FROM THE PROJECT LIAISON

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1. Introduction

In recent years, notions such as ‘innovation support services’, ‘innovation facilitation’, and ‘innovation brokerage’ have become more and more commonplace in the field of agricultural innovation in many countries. While the use of these termini is not unified (cf. Ndash et al. 2018: 6f.), their overall emergence testifies to a *paradigm shift* in thinking about agricultural innovation. They represent the growing acknowledgment that innovation processes are *complex* – and in fact are becoming increasingly so – and therefore demand for the cooperation of multiple actors. In this perspective, *enabling coordinated action in a broad network of actors with various backgrounds* becomes a crucial function in innovation processes. It is precisely this function of ‘enabling’, which the above notions – with somewhat varying connotations – aim to capture.

Core actors engaged in the Common Agricultural Policy have picked up the terminology of ‘innovation support services’ and ‘innovation brokerage’ as well (cf. EC 2014). Some of them such as the *Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development* (DG Agri), the *EIP-Agri Service Point* (2014, 2019), and the *Strategic Working Group of the Standing Committee of Agricultural Research on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation*

Systems (SWG SCAR AKIS) propose that, ideally, *farm advisory services* (FAS)¹ should take over these functions. They suggest that “**farm advisory services** can act as good innovation brokers or innovation support services because they have broad networks and [are] well-positioned to bring the right people together” (EIP-Agri SP 2019, emphasises in the original). In order to be able to perform this role, it is suggested that FAS should receive greater public financial and institutional support and be more involved in the development of agricultural policies and programmes than in the past (SWG SCAR AKIS 2017: 1; DG Agri 2019: 5).

This paper aims to better assess which types of organisations are currently acting as ‘innovation support services’, and if FAS are indeed as central to the performance of this role as the above claim suggests. For that purpose, we will first offer a short review of the general evolution of the concepts of ‘innovation support services’, ‘innovation brokerage’ etc. and make their relation to each other more transparent (2). Then, following an overview of the applied methods for data collection (3), we present some research findings from the H2020 project LIAISON² on 200 interactive innovation projects and initiatives³ from the agri-food and forestry sectors that may shed some light onto the actual functional set-up of innovation processes (4). We argue that these findings indicate that, rather than farm advisors only, in practice various types of organisations provide innovation support services in agriculture. This confirms other research on that issue (cf. Faure et al. 2019; Ndah et al. 2018; Klerkx and Gildermacher 2012; Klerkx et al. 2012). We conclude that policies aimed at supporting participatory innovation processes

¹ Note that while these actors generally translate FAS as ‘farm advisory services’, they are actually referring to the national *farm advisory systems* according to EU REGULATION No 1306/2013 of 17 December 2013 on the financing, management and monitoring of the common agricultural policy. Title III, Art. 12 of the Regulation states that “Member States shall establish a system for advising beneficiaries on land management and farm management (‘farm advisory system’); and that farm advisory system shall be operated by designated public bodies and/or selected private bodies”. Farm advisory systems are supposed to offer advice to farmers on, among else, the legal obligations that result from EU agricultural regulation, e.g. with regard to environmental standards, as well as on “measures at farm level provided for in rural development programmes for farm modernisation, competitiveness building, sectoral integration, innovation and market orientation [...]”. Importantly, as the article explicitly states, the organisations that participate in the national farm advisory system may be either public or private bodies. However, they are subject to EU- and national, i.e. public regulation. When the DG Agri et al. – as we will shortly see – juxtapose the farm advisory services they wish to strengthen to ‘private’ or ‘commercial’ farm advice, this is thus due to the fact by farm advisory services they really mean the national farm advisory systems of the EU member states. However, this distinction will be less relevant in this paper, since we will review the role of farm advisory organisations in supporting agricultural innovation more generally, not just of specific types (public/private) of advisory organisations.

² The H2020 project LIAISON (<http://liaison2020.eu/>) was launched in 2018 with the intention to contribute to the optimization of interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. One key concern of the project is the identification of success conditions and challenges to collaboration in interactive innovative projects, i.e., projects in which various types of actors such as farmers, researchers, advisors and consumer organisations are actively involved.

³ A project is carefully planned to achieve a particular aim and is characterized by a defined start and end. In contrast, networks and initiatives can be ongoing and can come from or lead to projects (cf. O’Neill et al. 2012).

should focus on the *functions* provided by organisations in these processes instead of devoting special attention to a particular *type* of organisation (5).

2. Conceptual background: innovation support services, innovation brokerage, innovation facilitation

2.1 Conceptual clarification

The use of the concepts of ‘innovation support services’, ‘innovation brokerage’ and the like is not unified in the field of agriculture: both researchers and practitioners use the terms differently (cf. Ndah et al. 2018). Some authors operate with quite clear-cut conceptual distinctions. The EIP-Agri Service Point, for instance, distinguishes between ‘innovation support services’ as a more general term, which “covers various tasks that support innovation”. They see ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ as two distinct of these supporting tasks. In their definition, ‘innovation brokerage’ takes place in the *initial stages* of the cooperation for innovation and entails the following activities: 1. the discovery of innovative ideas; 2. “connecting potential partners with complementary knowledge, competences and infrastructure” (‘match-making’, EIP-Agri SP 2014: 3) and “taking the initiative to help them to refine the innovative idea” (EIP-Agri SP 2014: 3); 3. identifying funding sources and providing partners with a solid understanding of what criteria need to be fulfilled in order to make an application for financing (EIP-Agri SP 2014: 4); and 4. the preparation of a project proposal, which all actors involved can endorse. In contrast, ‘innovation facilitation’ refers to mediating activities that “bridge the language of science/markets and entrepreneurial practice” (EIP-Agri SP 2019). Unlike ‘innovation brokerage’, this kind of mediation needs to be performed not only at the initial stages, but continuously during the project cooperation. According to the EIP-Agri Service Point, the supporting tasks of ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ may (but need not) be performed by the same person.

Similar to the EIP-Agri Service Point, Faure et al. (2019) use ‘innovation support services’ as an umbrella term for all activities that support cooperation and co-creation for innovation. Drawing on other studies on ‘innovation support services’ in agriculture, they offer a distinction of several sub-tasks of such services. Among these tasks are “awareness and exchange of knowledge” or “networks, facilitation and brokerage”, the latter referring to the “provision of services to help organise or strengthen networks [...]” (Faure et al. 2019: 151). So, while the authors do not distinguish as clearly between the tasks of ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ as the EIP-Agri Service Point, it is obvious that they as well consider them sub-categories of the broader concept of ‘innovation support services’.

In contrast, Klerkx et al. (2012) and Klerkx and Gildemacher (2012) use the term ‘innovation brokerage’ in a broad sense that is analogous to the EIP-Agri Service Point’s understanding of ‘innovation support services’. In their definition, innovation brokerage is

not the name of a sub-task of innovation support that should be performed in the project development phase only, but instead “be applied in a flexible and iterative manner” (Klerkx and Gildemacher 2012: 222) throughout the project. The authors propose that it is dividable into three distinct tasks, namely 1. context analysis and demand articulation (assessment of problems and opportunities), 2. network composition (“facilitat[ing] linkages among relevant actors”), and 3. facilitating interaction (cf. Klerkx and Gildemacher 2012: 222f.). In this understanding, then, innovation brokerage and innovation facilitation become indistinguishable, with ‘innovation brokerage’ serving as a general concept that captures, besides ‘narrow’ brokerage tasks, also facilitating or mediating activities.

Still other actors are using all three of these concepts interchangeably or at least without any obvious differentiation. For example, in a recent policy document the DG Agri proposes that advisors should “collect farmers’ needs” and “feed these needs and opportunities into the AKIS [Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System] for further development – **possibly as an ‘innovation support service’**” (DG Agri 2019: 6, emphasis in the original). In the pursuing sentence, they say “[f]arm advisors within the AKIS should also be trained to act as **innovation brokers/facilitators**” (ibid. emphasis in the original). How exactly ‘innovation support services’, ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ relate to each other, and if they in fact designate different roles at all, remains somewhat vague.

As these few examples already demonstrate, the concepts of ‘innovation support services’, ‘innovation brokerage’, and ‘innovation facilitation’ are not used consistently in the agricultural field. For the remainder of this paper, however, we will adopt the EIP-Agri’s conceptual distinction. That is, we will use ‘innovation support services’ (hereafter ISS) as the overarching notion, and to ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ as two distinct sub-tasks of innovation support that are performed at the beginning of or during the project, respectively. This terminology promises to avoid conceptual confusion. In addition, it seems to be particularly influential, as it informs European agricultural policy.

2.2 Background: paradigm shift in thinking about innovation

Although the respective meanings of the concepts of ISS, innovation brokerage and innovation facilitation may be somewhat ambiguous and difficult to discern, their overall emergence mirrors a paradigm shift in thinking about agricultural innovation. It testifies to the gradual transition of an understanding that considers research the main driving factor of innovation towards a ‘systemic’ understanding that recognizes that innovation requires the coordination of a much wider network of actors and activities. It is only against the background of this *broadened notion of innovation* that the concept of ‘innovation-supporting activities’ that help this coordination becomes relevant (cf. Koutsouris 2014; Ndah et al. 2018: 2; Klerkx and Gildemacher 2012: 221).

For many decades, agricultural policies in the EU have been informed by a ‘linear approach’ to agricultural innovation “in which new knowledge is developed through research, distributed through advisory and education services and then practically implemented by entrepreneurs” (Détang-Dessendre et al. 2018: 11). However, this approach has been increasingly criticised for not being fit to cope with the complex social reality of most innovation processes. In particular, it did not respond enough to differences between agricultural production contexts and complex natural resource management conflicts (cf. Klerkx et al. 2012: 54; Faure et al. 2019: 149).

These shortcomings led to a *first change* in the concept and practice of agricultural extension: participatory approaches to agricultural innovation emerged, whose main objective it was “to enhance research uptake and impact [...] by adapting research to specific contexts and creating ownership of the research” (Klerkx et al. 2012: 54). This more inclusive perspective considered, next to the bilateral relation between farmers and research, “the broader knowledge systems in which farmers were embedded” (ibid.), or what was then labelled the ‘Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems’ (AKIS).⁴

However, this adjusted approach to agricultural innovation still retained a narrow focus on research and did not recognize the importance of other, not research-related activities. Agricultural extension was largely identified with ‘*knowledge brokering*’, i.e. the facilitation of knowledge exchange between research and practice (Klerkx et al. 2012: 54). It thus remained in a linear “transfer of technology and information framework” (Faure et al. 2019: 148), even while it had been “fine-tuned by scholars to take into account the diversity of technologies or the diversity of farmers” (ibid).

The introduction of the roles of the ‘innovation broker’ and the ‘innovation facilitator’ finally represent a shift to an *even more holistic understanding of innovation* which acknowledges that “research does not equal innovation” (Klerkx et al. 2012: 55). In this perspective, innovation consists not just in the development of new technologies but requires the active management of the interplay between these technical solutions and established social practices. In such a changed understanding, next to *knowledge gaps* between actors, “several other divides among groups involved in innovation and development” (Klerkx et al. 2012: 57) such as differences in interests/values and incentives that hinder effective collaboration have to be bridged as well. Against this background, innovation support is not something that some providers deliver to ‘passive’ beneficiaries in the form of linear advice (Faure et al. 2019: 148ff.). Instead, it is performed through a mutual and interactive learning process, where borders between ‘providers’ and ‘beneficiaries’ of support blur and the exchange of knowledge replaces linear instruction.

2.3 Farm advisors as innovation brokers/facilitators?

One key issue that emerges repeatedly in discussions related to innovation support services is the question of *who* is actually performing these services or who *should* perform

⁴ More recently re-labelled *Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System*, cf. Faure et al. 2019:147.

them, and why. Many studies show that, with the increasing (acknowledgment of the) complexity of agricultural innovation processes, the division of labour between innovation partners becomes more complex as well. While traditional agricultural extension was typically performed by farm advisors who instructed farmers on “how to act to improve their farms” (Faure et al. 2019: 148), today’s more complex ISS vary greatly from context to context, with a variety of actors taking over different tasks in support of innovation (cf. Faure et al. 2019: 150; Ndah et al. 2018: 4f.). In one case, for instance, a private business might act as innovation broker together with a NGO as innovation facilitator, while in another agricultural industry or administrative context; these roles might be split among several organisations. Alternatively, an advisory organisation might provide both services, ‘innovation brokerage’ and facilitation at the same time due to the regional infrastructure.

By contrast, as mentioned above, some central actors involved in EU agricultural policy making are currently calling specifically on farm advisory organisations to take on the roles of innovation brokers and facilitators. Organisations such as DG Agri and the EIP-Agri Service Point in particular as well as some think tanks like the *Strategic Working Group of the Standing Committee of Agricultural Research on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems* (SWG SCAR AKIS) suggest that farm advisors are especially suited to perform task that support interactive innovation. For instance, on a website entry on “Innovation support services (including advisers with a focus on innovation)”, the EIP-Agri Service Point (2019) argue that “[m]any advisers are ideally positioned to set up and join groups that deal with technical, financial, social, environmental or market-related issues and problems. They established a trust-based relationship, which enables them to act as brokers and which brings together farmers and others actors who can help each other”. In a similar vein, the DG Agri (2019) highlights that “advisors play a key role to collect farmers’ needs and opportunities, thanks to their one-to-one interactions with farmers while giving advice. They should feed these needs and opportunities back into the AKIS for further development – **possibly as an ‘innovation support service’** – helping the knowledge systems to improve their impact” (DG Agri 2019: 6, emphasis in the original).

Since the activities of ‘innovation brokerage’ and ‘innovation facilitation’ go beyond the ‘linear advice’ that FAS traditionally performed, it is argued that FAS will need more public financial support or “a mix of public and private funding” (SWG SCAR AKIS 2017:7) as well better institutional backup than they currently have. In addition, they should be more involved in agricultural policy making, since “[s]upporting an interactive role of advisors already in the early stage of definition of policies and programmes would help creating an enabling environment to better connect practice and science” (SWG SCAR AKIS 2017:3). Without this improvement of FAS, they fear that corporate advisors, who are independent from FAS, will take over the provision of ‘innovation support services’ instead.⁵ This will not only disadvantage small farming businesses that often cannot afford to pay for private advice, but also threaten the ideal of impartial farm advice since

⁵ On the distinction between FAS and non-FAS-related private farm advice, see footnote 1 above.

private advisory organisations have profit interests to consider (SWG SCAR AKIS 2017: 1; DG Agri 2019: 5).

This line of reasoning suggests that it is in a way ‘natural’ that advisory organisations should provide ISS. The required policy decision, in this view, is that between increasing public support for existing FAS, and surrendering innovation support to FAS-independent private advisors. In the remainder of this paper, we will re-evaluate this argument. While it raises some important concerns, we venture that it rests on a somewhat *narrow* understanding of agricultural innovation since it seems to assume that advisory organisations are the main providers of innovation support. In the following sections, we will present and discuss some preliminary findings from research in the H2020 research project *LIAISON* that suggest that other organisations such as research institutes, NGOs, producer organisations as well as agricultural education providers can take over innovation support services as well.

3. Methodology

3.1 Light Touch Review of 200 innovative projects in agriculture and forestry

In the framework of *LIAISON*, 200 innovative projects and initiatives in the agri-food and forestry sectors throughout Europe were subjected to a ‘light touch review’ (LTR). This consisted of a desk study of published material of each project (e.g. website, public documents) as well as a ‘one telephone call’ semi-structured interview with a key informant (e.g. the coordinator). The purpose of this review was to identify the main traits of these projects and initiatives and to determine best practices as well as challenges to collaboration both within the project and between the project consortium, external stakeholders and funding bodies. Projects and initiatives were partially identified through databases of the funding programmes Horizon 2020, INTERREG Europe and LIFE and national databases, and partially through a Europe-wide Rural Innovation Contest (EURIC) launched by the *LIAISON* consortium in 2019.⁶

The selection of the reviewed 200 cases from all identified projects and initiatives was based on three criteria:

- The ‘insightfulness’ of the project (i.e. its relevance and/or information-richness with relation to the issue of interactive innovation);
- The availability of a suitable contact person who can provide insight into collaborative processes within the project
- Funding source of the project or initiative: in each country, a set of projects and initiatives with diverse funding schemes were reviewed.

⁶ 750 interactive projects and initiatives were identified through research of EU and national databases, and 229 additional companies, projects and initiatives from 21 EU member states and two EU neighbouring states entered applications to the EURIC.

3.2 Data from the LTR relevant to the research on ISS in agriculture and forestry

Although the LTR was not conducted with the explicit aim of identifying innovation support service providers, the gathered data still offer insights on current features of ISS in agriculture and forestry. The following information from the LTR are particularly relevant in this regard:

- First, an overview of the *types of organisations that are coordinating the studied projects*. As we have seen before, most usages of the terms ‘innovation brokerage’ or ‘innovation facilitation’ consider ‘coordination’ of multi-actor processes a central part of these roles. In order to assess the importance of FAS as providers of such innovation support services, it may therefore be helpful to look at *who is actually taking over the role of the coordinator in interactive innovative projects in agriculture*. In section 4.1, we will present the pertaining LTR findings from all reviewed 200 projects and initiatives, gained through desktop surveys and verified in semi-structured interviews with project participants.⁷
- Second, information about the actual *reasons for the choice of the coordinating organisation*, which was obtained through telephone interviews (“What were the reasons underpinning the selection of the project coordinator?”). Based on the arguments given by the interviewees, we clustered their answers into different categories while allowing for multiple answers. Their responses illuminate which features in an organisation project members consider necessary for the performance of coordination and thus, of innovation brokerage and facilitation. In this way, they may also *help to understand the current extent to which FAS are performing these roles* in interactive innovation projects in agriculture. Since this paper focuses on the status of farm advisors in interactive innovation in the EU in particular, in section 4.2 we will present the findings from projects funded or co-funded by the EU⁸ only, which is the case for 108 out of the 200 reviewed projects.
- Thirdly, information on the performance of two other tasks that are associated with ‘*innovation brokerage*’ in the more narrow sense, namely the initial ‘*match-making*’ between actors and the proposal-writing. This information was obtained through two further interview questions of the LTR: “How was the project set up?” and “Who took charge of the proposal writing process and why?”. In case of the first question, answers were again clustered and multiple answers allowed. We present the responses of the interviewees from the 108 reviewed EU (co-)funded projects to these two questions in section 4.3.

⁷ We are well aware that the kind of funding a project receives will likely affect its features— such as for instance the choice of the coordinator or the role of advisory organisations within the project. For that reason, we attempted to cover a wide range of different types of EU-funded, co-funded and non-funded projects and included the type of funding as one variable in our assessment template. However, in this paper, we will not differentiate between different types of project-funding but only present general trends across the reviewed projects. More elaborated hypotheses on the causal links between the type of funding and the functional set-up of projects remains a topic for further research.

⁸ These are (i) projects funded in the H2020 Research and Innovation scheme (RIA), (ii) Thematic Networks (TN), which are Coordination and Support Actions (CSA), (iii) Operational Groups (OG) funded under the Rural Development Programmes of the Member States, and (iv) Interreg projects.

4. Preliminary findings

4.1 Desk survey results: coordination of innovative projects (n = 200)

If advisory organisations were indeed in a privileged position to perform the roles of innovation broker and facilitator in innovation projects in agriculture, one would expect them to be listed as project coordinators more often than other types of organisation. However, quantitative findings from the desk surveys conducted in the course of the LIAISON LTR do not confirm this expectation. Different types of organisations such as research and education institutions, businesses, individual farmers, representative/supporting institutions, public bodies, NGOs and processing/ marketing organisations led the projects. Of the studied projects, the largest share were coordinated by research organisations (30,5%), followed by farmers' representing/supporting organisations (12%), NGOs (12%), public bodies (11%), and businesses (7%). Only 4% of the project coordinators were classified as advisory organisations. The large number of projects coordinated by research institutions might be less surprising in projects that focus on policy programmes such as the H2020 RIA scheme (n= 34). In other cases such as the Thematic Networks funded under the H2020 CSA scheme (n= 16), however, we would have expected more advisory organisations to be listed as coordinators. Yet we find that none of the studied Thematic Network projects was coordinated by an advisory organisation.

Importantly, if there are only few advisory organisations among the coordinators of the studied projects, this is not because their participation in these projects would have been generally low. In fact, while research organisations were the type of organisation that was most frequently listed as project participants (155 times), advisory organisations participated at least in 104 projects – about as often as representative/supporting organisations (111 times) and processing/marketing businesses (106) and significantly more often than public bodies (91) or NGOs (76).

4.2 Telephone interview results: reasons for choosing the coordinator (n=108)

Most of the interviewees from the reviewed 108 EU (co-)funded projects stated that the choice of the coordinator was in a way a 'natural' consequence of the coordinator's *pre-existing relation to the project*. That was the case e.g. where the coordinator had also developed the project idea or had been coordinating a precedent project (46 out of 108 interviews). Other important reasons for the choice of coordinator were the respective organisation's *expertise in proposal writing and/or project coordination* (36 out of 108) and its *availability of resources* (time, money, staff) (34 out of 108). Only a minority of the interviewees said that an external entity had been involved as a coordinator (9 out of 108), or that a formal 'Innovation Support Service' or 'Innovation Broker' were in charge of the coordination (6 out of 108).

These results help to illuminate why advisors are underrepresented among project coordinators, compared to their actual participation quote. They indicate that, rather than the specific *type* of organisation, what matters in the decision about whom to appoint

as project coordinator is in fact a collective assessment of an organisation's *fitness* for that role. Apparently, the organisation to which a project consortium ascribes this fitness the most varies from project to project.

4.3 Telephone interview results: 'match-making' and proposal-writing (n=108)

In some of the reviewed EU (co-)funded projects, one of the consortium members took the leading role in initiating the project and invited other project partners (26 out of 108). 34 of the other projects evolved from previously existing formal and informal relationships between participants and thus in a way emerged, as one interviewee framed it, as the "logical next step". In these latter cases, no project partner took a particular leadership role in the setting-up of the project. In 22 cases, some members of the consortium knew each other from existing cooperation while others were invited to complete the group. Eight interviewees stated that a governmental organisation set up the project.⁹

These answers indicate that no specific type of organisation acted as innovation broker or initial 'match-maker'. Rather, projects either typically emerged either from previous links between the participants, or from one partner's (independent of the specific type of organisation he represents) active rallying of participants, or from a combination of both.

The findings on the organisation of the proposal writing in these reviewed projects are in line with that. The majority of the interviewees reported that the project initiator took charge of the proposal writing (57 out of 108). 24 interviewees named the expertise or formal capacity of the proposal writer as decisive factors, while 37 interviewees indicated that the members of their project's core group had shared responsibility for the proposal writing. Only nine interviewees stated that the group hired an external expert, and only three said that an official innovation support service wrote the proposal.

Here too, then, other factors than the actual type of organisation seem to affect the collective choice of who is taking charge of the proposal writing. Attribution of this role seems to depend on previous developments within the project consortium, such as established patterns of interaction between the partners and/or whether some partner was particularly involved in the initiation of the project idea. Finally, actors' expertise in proposal writing and experience and recognition in the field are decisive in the distribution of tasks.

⁹ in eight cases, the answers were not clearly attributable to any of these response categories.

5 Discussion of findings

Overall, these data allow for some tentative conclusions as to the status of innovation support services in agriculture and forestry and the role which different types of organisations play in the provision of these services. One conclusion is that ISS provision is not a prerogative of specific organisations. This is because just as innovation processes become more multifaceted, so do the tasks that are required in order to initiate and facilitate innovation. Many more kinds of social divisions need to be overcome between a much wider range of actors, beyond “bridging the divide between research and practice”. This may include conflicts or other discrepancies among farmers themselves, or between farmers and businesses or NGOs. In order to enable coordinated action between these actors, the social and institutional setting in which they operate will need to be changed before innovation can become effective. These brokerage and facilitation tasks, however, can be performed by *various kinds of actors*, since their successful execution depends less on specific organisational features than on experience in mediation activities and trust-based relationships within the relevant field. This interpretation confirms results from other research (cf. Klerkx et al. 2012; Faure et al. 2019).

If that is the case, however, how do we make sense of the DG Agri’s, the SWG SCAR AKIS’ and others’ proposal that farm advisors are particularly well suited to act as innovation brokers/facilitators? One possible analysis is that while these actors refer to the *labels* of ‘**innovation** brokerage’ and the like, the actual *framework* they apply is in fact still very much that of **knowledge** brokerage, i.e., a “transfer of technology and information framework” (Faure et al. 2019: 148). A closer reading of the above-mentioned policy papers indicates that in these actors’ understanding of innovation, the transfer of research results into agricultural practice is still conceived as the core of innovation. While ‘linear advice’ may not be the most appropriate medium for innovation anymore, the *facilitation of coordination between science and practice*, or research and farming still appears to be the central focus of innovation-supporting interventions. From the premises of such an understanding of innovation, however, it is indeed reasonable to ascribe FAS a crucial supporting role, since the role of the intermediary between research and farming practice is the very role they have traditionally performed and that they have specialized in.

However, while such an approach may work out in some cases (cf. Faure et al. 2017), it will likely prove to be too reductive in more complex cases of innovation. If innovation support focuses too much on the optimisation of *knowledge* transfers between researchers and practice, or even among practitioners, we risk losing track of the various other linking activities that are required today to enable innovation in agriculture. Therefore, if policy-makers are thinking of ways to strengthen ISS in agriculture, rather than channelling support to specific *types of organisation*, they ought to make sure that the *functions that enable and facilitate innovation* are performed.

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